

International Journal of Plant Science and Horticulture

Research Article

Open Access

New Prediction Models of Innovative Technologies for Maximising the Production of Greengram and Blackgram in Coastal Areas of India

Pandiyan M^{1*}, Sivakumar P², Sivakumar C¹, Krishnaveni A^{1#}, Radhakrishnan V¹, Jamuna E¹ and Vaithiyalingan M¹

¹Agricultural College & Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Vazhavachanur, Tiruvannamalai, Tamil Nadu, India

²Agricultural College & Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Eachankottai, Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu, India

***Corresponding Author:** Pandiyan M, Agricultural College Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Vazhavachanur - 606 753 Tiruvannamalai District, Tamil Nadu, India, Email: mpandiyan8@yahoo.co.in

#Co-Corresponding author: Krishnaveni A, Email: venikrishna25@yahoo.co.in

Received Date: Dec 18, 2019 / **Accepted Date:** Jan 06, 2019 / **Published Date:** Jan 09, 2019

Abstract

Pulse crops are having rich source of proteins and its plays major role in giving nutritionally balanced diet for vegetarian's humans. India is the major consumer, producer and highest importer of pulses. However, pulses yields are mostly affected input limits particularly fertilizers, quality seeds and lifesaving irrigation was not sufficient associated to cereal crops such as rice and wheat. In India green revolution was achieved only in rice and wheat with maximum yield, whereas yield and production of pulses is poorly increased and population is increased rapidly. In current situation, enhancing the pulse production with various new prediction models of innovative technologies for maximising the production of green gram and black gram in coastal areas is highly essential. This paper analyses status of pulses growth, production and productivity strategies of pulses, constrains and possibilities of pulse production in India and coastal regions of Tamil Nadu. Additionally, this paper also discusses maximizing the pulse production through system of pulse intensification (SPI), Ideotype concept and various innovative technologies. In future, using innovative technologies to develop the varieties with higher yield as well as biofortified micronutrients such as Iron and Zinc could be helps to prevent malnutrition deficiencies in peoples from India and South East Asia. Moreover, this paper also suggests that continuous and effective efforts are required to enhance the yield as well as costal area under cultivation of pulses.

Keywords: Black gram; Green gram; Ideotype concept; Innovative technologies; Pulses; Production

Cite this article as: Pandiyan M, Sivakumar P, Sivakumar C, et al. 2020. New Prediction Models of Innovative Technologies for Maximising the Production of Greengram and Blackgram in Coastal Areas of India. Int J Plant Sci Hor. 2: 12-18.

Copyright: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. Copyright © 2020; Pandiyan M

**New Prediction Models of Innovative Technologies for Maximising
the Production of Greengram and Blackgram in Coastal Areas of India**

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36811/ijpsh.2020.110020>

IJPSH: January-2020: Page No: 12-18

Full-length manuscript: https://www.raftpubs.com/ijpsh-plant-science-and-horticulture/articles/ijpsh_raft1020.php

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36811/ijpsh.2020.110020>

More Articles: <https://www.raftpubs.com/ijpsh-plant-science-and-horticulture/archive.php>